

Makalah Ilmiah

The Effect of Gamma Irradiation on the Metal Adsorption Efficiency of Surfactant-Modified Activated Carbon (SMAC)

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THE EFFECT OF GAMMA IRRADIATION ON THE METAL ADSORPTION EFFICIENCY OF SURFACTANT-MODIFIED ACTIVATED CARBON (SMAC)

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ABSTRACT

Effect of Gamma Irradiation on Metal Sorption Efficiency of Surfactant Modified Activated Carbon (SMAC). This study explored the effect of activated carbon modification using surfactants and gamma irradiation on its adsorption ability to Cu^{2+} metal ions. The activated carbon used was sieved to 70 mesh size, then contacted with Sodium Lauryl Sulfate (SLS) surfactant solution and irradiated with a dose of 30 kGy. The irradiation process aims to enlarge the pores of activated carbon, increase the absorbency of surfactants, and ultimately increase the efficiency of metal adsorption. The results showed that the irradiated activated carbon had a higher sorption efficiency compared to the non-irradiated one, with a decrease in Cu^{2+} concentration from 48.5 ppm to 35.4 ppm. The non-irradiated activated carbon was only able to reduce the Cu^{2+} concentration to 46.83 ppm. This finding indicates that the combination of surfactant modification and gamma irradiation can significantly increase the adsorption capacity of activated carbon.

Keywords: Activated Carbon, Gamma Irradiation, Adsorption, Metal Ions

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, many researchers have been carried out to design and improve effective adsorbents [1]. The chemical and physical properties of adsorbents play a crucial role in the adsorption process. Chemically, the presence and type of functional groups on the adsorbent surface are important. Physically, adsorbent can exist in various forms such as powders or granules, and their surface area and pore size significantly influence adsorption performance [2]. One method to enhance the surface properties of adsorbents is through the use of surfactants. Surfactant-Modified Activated Carbon (SMAC) is a product derived from modifying activated carbon with surfactants, which can improve the adsorption capacity for ions [3]. The application of surfactants to activated carbon can increase its adsorption efficiency for metal ions.

In addition to surfactant modification, gamma irradiation of the surfactant-modified activated carbon can further enhance the adsorption performance, primarily by increasing the surface area of the adsorbent. Saha et al, reported that the porosity of polyethylene oxide (PEO) powder increased with gamma irradiation up to a dose of 3 kGy and then decreased linearly as the dose was increased from 3 to 30 kGy [4]. Therefore, this study investigates the gamma irradiation of surfactant-modified activated carbon to improve its metal adsorption capacity and explore its potential application in industrial wastewater treatment.

METHODOLOGY

The activated carbon used in this study was commercially available activated carbon. It was first sieved to 70 mesh particle size, and 12,5 grams were taken for further processing. The activated carbon was then contacted with 250 ml of surfactant solution. The surfactant used was Sodium Lauryl Sulfate (SLS), prepared by dissolving was stirred using a mechanical shaker for 24 hours. Afterward, the sample was irradiated with a gamma dose of 30 kGy. Following irradiation, the activated carbon was filtered and dried at a temperature of 80°C until a constant weight was achieved. A stock solution Cu^{2+} with a concentration 1000 ppm was prepared using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. From the stock, 48,5 ppm was prepared, as well as standard solutions with concentrations of 0 ppm, 10 ppm, 20 ppm, 30 ppm, 40 ppm and 50 ppm for calibration purposes. Subsequently, 0,5 grams of the dried, surfactant-modified and irradiated activated carbon and the filtrate was analyzed using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer to determine change in Cu^{2+} Concentration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Absorbance (ABS) of Standard Curve of Cu²⁺

Concentration	Absorbance (ABS)	Equation	Note
0	0,361	abs = 0,014695x+0,359765	R2 = 0,9881
10	0,529		
20	0,649		
30	0,771		
40	0,91		
50	1,137		

This study utilized gamma rays for the irradiation process. Prior to contacting the activated carbon with the Cu²⁺ solution, a series of standard solutions were prepared. A linear calibration equation was obtained: $y = 0,014695x + 0,359765$ with correlation coefficient (r) of 0,9881, indicating a strong linear relationship. After the calibration, of the Cu²⁺ solution was contacted with the activated carbon for 30 minutes.

Tabel 2. Comparison of Metal Adsorption

Initial ABS	Initial Concentration	Dose	Final ABS Values	Average Final ABS	Final Concentration	
1,073	48,5 ppm	0 kGy	1,051	1,048	46,83 ppm	
			1,048			
			1,046			
		30 kGy	0,87	0,88		35,4 ppm
			0,91			
			0,88			

Based on the comparison table of metal adsorption, it can be observed that gamma irradiated carbon activated carbon exhibits a higher metal adsorption capacity compared to non-irradiated carbon. UV-Vis spectrophotometric analysis showed that non irradiated activated carbon reduced the concentration of Cu²⁺ in solution to 46,83 ppm. In contrast, resulting in final metal concentration of 35,4 ppm in solution. Liu et al. [5] modified bamboo based activated carbon using microwave heating, which led to an increase in the pore diameter of the carbon. Similarly, Abas et al. [6] reported that microwave treatment could enhance the surface area of activated carbon. Likewise, gamma irradiation can also cause pore expansion in the carbon structure, allowing more surfactant molecules to be incorporated into the carbon matrix. The increased surfactant content in activated carbon enhances its ability to adsorb metal ions.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that gamma irradiation significantly enhances the adsorption performance of surfactant-modified activated carbon (SMAC). The irradiated SMAC demonstrated superior metal ion adsorption efficiency compared to its non-irradiated counterpart. This improvement is likely attributed to the structural modifications induced by gamma irradiation, which may include an increase in surface area and porosity, as well as potential changes in surface chemistry. These enhancements facilitate greater interaction between the active adsorption sites on the carbon surface and metal ions in solution, thereby improving the overall adsorption capacity of the material.

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